

Design, synthesis and molecular recognition properties of pyridine-based hetero bis amide receptors

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Abstract : Two new pyridine-based hetero bis amide receptors **1** and **2** has been designed and synthesized. The recognition properties of these newly formed receptors were investigated by ¹H NMR, UV-Vis spectroscopy and fluorescence methods. They are found to be effective in hosting α -hydroxy and α -amino acid derivatives into the open clefts.

Keywords : Hetero bis amide receptors, α -hydroxy acids, α -amino acids, hydrogen bonding.

Introduction

Synthesis of structurally simple receptors for guests of biological significance is a continuous endeavor in host-guest chemistry¹. Incorporation of amide functionality in the design of such simple receptors is considered to be elegant because of the moderate hydrogen bonding ability and special structural feature of the amide linkage². The presence of other hydrogen bonding groups along with this amide functionality in a specific design sometimes creates an environment for hosting useful small guest molecules. In this context, the hetero bis amide receptors with many other hydrogen bonding groups are interesting³. Given the biomimetic importance on monocarboxylic acids like hydroxy and amino acids, we find that there have been a series of synthetic receptors and many of them are structurally complex. In order to study the interaction of such kind of guest molecules, we became interested in the synthesis of receptors combining pyridine amide as carboxylic acid binder with other hydrogen bonding groups under the control of semi rigid spacer.

In designing artificial receptors for α -hydroxy and α -amino acids, we took the following two different following strategies (Fig. 1). In both cases the hydrogen bonding groups of the receptors converge to the guests for successful binding. With the aim of development of receptors based on these strategies, two different amines were coupled to semi rigid isophthaloyl spacer. Pyridine amine was considered as the carboxylic acid binding motif⁴. Thus three coplanar hydrogen bonds can be obtained

Fig. 1. Design strategies for the synthesis of **1** and **2**.

from two different amides and pyridine ring nitrogen to bind carboxylic acid via three point hydrogen bonds⁵.

We reasoned that this approach would be very simple and manageable. In this paper, we report the synthesis of pyridine-based hetero bis amide receptors **1** and **2** and uncover the design criterion that control the selectivity and sensitivity towards α -heteroatom substituted monocarboxylic acids such as hydroxy and amino acids.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

In pursuit of developing hetero bis amide receptors, two different amines were coupled to semi rigid isophthaloyl spacer under high dilution condition in one step to afford the receptors **1** and **2**. Pyridine amine was considered in both cases as the carboxylic acid binding motif. Schemes 1 and 2 describes the synthesis of both **1** and **2**. The receptor **1** was obtained as white gummy product by coupling of 2-amino-6-methylpyridine and long chain polyether amine **5** with isophthaloyl dichloride in a single step (Scheme 1). The long chain polyether amine **5** was prepared from diethyleneglycol monobutyl ether **3** through a series of reactions. Reaction of **3** with SOCl_2 in the presence of pyridine gave the compound **4**, which was transformed into the corresponding azide compound on reaction with NaN_3 in acetone solvent. Subsequent reduction of the azide by PPh_3 in water-THF⁶ mixture solvent afforded the amine **5**. On the other hand, compound **7** for the synthesis of **2**, was obtained from 2-(*N*-pivaloylamino)-6-bromomethylpyridine via etherification followed by amide hydrolysis (Scheme 2). High dilution coupling reaction of compound **7** and dodecylamine with isophthaloyl dichloride in dry CH_2Cl_2 gave the hetero bis amide receptor **2** in 31% yield.

Molecular modeling⁷ :

To realize the orientation of the hydrogen bonding groups around the open diamide core and their participation in bonding with guests, we optimized the geometries of **1** and **2** with guests. The molecular modeling studies on the *syn*-form of **1** with the α -heteroatom substituted acids as mentioned such as *L-N*-acetylvaline, *L-N*-acetylphenyl alanine, *rac*-lactic and *D*-(-)-mandelic acids were performed. The optimized geometry of the 1 : 1 complex of **1** with *L-N*-acetylvaline shows the cooperative hydrogen bonding arrangements where two oxygen atoms of ether chain are involved in making hydrogen bonded five membered rings with the amide hydrogen of *L-N*-acetylvaline (Fig. 2A). Figs. 2B, 2C and 2D describe the optimized geometries of **1** with the other guests such as *L-N*-acetylphenyl alanine, lactic acid and *D*-(-)-mandelic acids, respectively. In all the cases the ether chain is involved in complexation, and the complex of **1** with *L-N*-acetylvaline is found to be relatively more stable than the others.

Receptor **2** was similarly optimized in the presence of the hydroxy acids and in each case the pyridine ring nitrogens are deeply involved in hydrogen bonding (Fig. 3). Importantly, the complex of **2** with *D*-(-)-mandelic acid exhibits marginally higher energy than the complex of **2** with *rac*-lactic acid.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of receptor **1** : *Reagents and conditions* : (i) SOCl_2 , pyridine, in dry CHCl_3 , reflux 10 h; (ii) NaN_3 in aqueous acetone, reflux, 12 h; (iii) PPh_3 in $\text{THF-H}_2\text{O}$; (iv) high dilution coupling with 2-amino-6-methylpyridine in presence of isophthaloyl dichloride in dry THF.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of receptor **2** : *Reagents and conditions*: (i) NaH , in dry THF, 2-pyridinemethanol; (ii) 4 *N* KOH in aqueous-ethanol, reflux, 16 h; (iii) high dilution coupling with dodecylamine in presence of isophthaloyl dichloride in dry THF.

Fig. 2. Energy minimized structures : (A) **1** with L-N-acetylvaline ($E = -3.15$ kcal/mol, $a = 2.08$ Å, $b = 2.12$ Å, $c = 1.49$ Å, $d = 2.78$ Å, $e = 2.06$ Å); (B) **1** with L-N-acetylphenyl alanine ($E = 1.16$ kcal/mol, $a = 2.07$ Å, $b = 2.09$ Å, $c = 1.55$ Å, $d = 1.96$ Å); (C) **1** with *rac*-lactic acid ($E = 2.28$ kcal/mol, $a = 2.02$ Å, $b = 2.07$ Å, $c = 1.53$ Å, $d = 1.92$ Å, $e = 2.53$ Å); (D) **1** with D-(-)-mandelic acid ($E = 7.26$ kcal/mol, $a = 2.0$ Å, $b = 2.1$ Å, $c = 1.54$ Å, $d = 2.03$ Å, $e = 2.31$ Å).

Fig. 3. Energy minimized structures : (A) **2** with D-(-)-mandelic acid ($E = 25.71$ kcal/mol, $a = 2.28$ Å, $b = 1.96$ Å, $c = 1.55$ Å, $d = 1.91$ Å); (B) **2** with *rac*-lactic acid ($E = 19.89$ kcal/mol, $a = 2.28$ Å, $b = 1.99$ Å, $c = 1.55$ Å, $d = 1.91$ Å).

Binding studies :

The placement of other hydrogen bonding groups in either side of the arms along with these three hydrogen bonds, cumulatively, may enhance host-guest interaction. In this context, the contribution of polyether chain of one arm is interesting in regard to selection of specific guest. In a similar way, modification of pyridine amide arm by adding an additional pyridine also shows a measurable effect in the selection of guest molecule. ^1H NMR spectroscopy was used to investigate the receptor-substrate interaction properties. It allowed access to the details of the interaction of both **1** and **2** with the α -hydroxy acid (such as *rac*-lactic acid and D-mandelic acid) and α -amino acid derivatives (such as L-N-acetylvaline and L-N-acetyl phenylalanine). Previously it has been reported that two point fixation of monocarboxylic acids with the amide derivative of 2-amino-6-methylpyridine shows weak binding ($2 \times 10^2 \text{ M}^{-1}$)⁸. To enhance the binding of the simple

pyridine amide moiety with mono carboxylic acids, which remain in highly associated form, the design and synthesis of hetero bisamide receptor was reported earlier^{3b}. There it was shown that the open cleft of hetero bisamide receptor bound carboxylic acid via three-point hydrogen bonding. In the present examples, we carried out the binding experiments with few representative α -heteroatom substituted monocarboxylic acids such as *rac*-lactic acid, D-(-)-mandelic acid and amide derivatives of L-valine, L-phenylalanine to establish the role of functional groups in the amide arms for the selection of a particular guest.

^1H NMR titration in CDCl_3 showed moderate binding and formation of 1 : 1 complex with the acid guests, such as L-N-acetylvaline, L-N-acetylphenylalanine, *rac*-lactic and D-(-)-mandelic acids. During titration both the amide protons (H_a and H_b) in **1** underwent downfield shift as shown in Table 1. The isophthaloyl peri proton also moved downfield ($\Delta\delta = 0.05\text{--}0.12$ ppm). This indicated the in-

Table 1. Change in chemical shift values of amide protons of **1** in the 1 : 1 complexes

Guest acid	$\Delta\delta$ for 'a' proton in ppm	$\Delta\delta$ for 'b' proton in ppm	Isophthaloyl peri proton in ppm
L-N-Acetylvaline	1.0	0.15	0.12
L-N-Acetylphenyl alanine	0.28	0.15	-0.01
rac-Lactic acid	1.1	0.69	0.12
D(-)-Mandelic acid	0.22	0.06	0.05

volvement of all the interacting groups in a cooperative manner to make 1 : 1 complexes with the guests.

The ether oxygen of **1** was also involved in complexation. This was confirmed by downfield shift of $-\text{CH}_2-$ protons, close to the amide linkage, although less in magnitude ($\Delta\delta = 0.05$ – 0.06 ppm). In a similar way, the receptor **2** was explored in binding with the same acid guests, used for **1** and was found to be involved in complexation with different selectivities. Here also both the amide protons (H_a and H_b) along with the isophthaloyl peri proton underwent downfield shift to the different extents (Table 2) upon complexation.

Table 2. Change in chemical shift values of amide protons of **2** in the 1 : 1 complexes

Guest acid	$\Delta\delta$ for 'a' proton in ppm	$\Delta\delta$ for 'b' proton in ppm	Isophthaloyl peri proton in ppm
L-N-Acetylvaline	0.11	0.03	0.12
L-N-Acetylphenyl alanine	0.36	0.38	-0.01
rac-Lactic acid	0.48	0.14	0.01
D(-)-Mandelic acid	0.66	0.07	0.08

To realize the binding strength of **1** and **2**, binding constant values were determined from ^1H NMR titration results⁹. The values are accumulated in Table 3. While the receptor **1** prefers L-N-acetylvaline, the receptor **2** binds D(-)-mandelic acid with relatively higher binding constant value. The lower magnitudes of binding constant values for **1** and **2** are attributed to the (i) self-association of hydroxy and amino acid derivatives and (ii) flexible nature of the receptors. The 1 : 1 stoichiometries of the

Table 3. Binding constants (K_a) of **1** and **2** with the guest acids

Guest acid	Receptor 1 (K_a in M^{-1}) by ^1H NMR in CDCl_3	Receptor 2 (K_a in M^{-1}) by ^1H NMR in CDCl_3
L-N-Acetylvaline	8.29×10^2	0.42×10^2
L-N-Acetylphenyl alanine	2.71×10^2	2.05×10^2
rac-Lactic acid	1.21×10^2	0.82×10^2
D(-)-Mandelic acid	0.51×10^2	3.07×10^2

complexes were ascertained from the breaks of the titration curves. Figs. 4 and 5 show the titration curves. Figs. 6 and 7 represent the binding constant curves for **1** and **2** with L-N-acetylvaline and D(-)-mandelic acid, respectively.

Fig. 5. NMR titration curve for **2** ($c = 5.39 \times 10^{-3}$ M). (●) D(-)-mandelic acid, (■) rac-lactic acid, (▲) L-N-acetylvaline, (▼) L-N-acetylphenylalanine.

Fig. 6. Binding constant determination curve of receptor **1** with L-N-acetylvaline from NMR.

Fig. 7. Binding constant determination curve of receptor **2** with D-(-)-mandelic acid from NMR.

Although there were no fluorescent probes in the designed receptors **1** and **2** for monitoring host-guest interactions, they were still examined in fluorescence. With a gradual increase in the concentration of the guest acids as mentioned in the Table 2, the fluorescence emission intensities of weakly fluorescent pyridine amide of receptor **1** at 375 nm ($\lambda_{ex} = 290$ nm) increased to the different extents (Fig. 8 for **1** and Fig. 9 for **2**). As shown in Fig. 9, receptor **1** displayed a fluorescence increasing effect upon addition of D-(-)-mandelic acid in $CHCl_3$.

Increase in fluorescence intensity of receptor **2** at 368 nm ($\lambda_{ex} = 290$ nm) was less compared to **1**. Figs. 10 and 11 shows the change in fluorescence intensity of **1** and **2**, upon addition of the guests in $CHCl_3$. These comparative views on receptors **1** and **2** in regard to their luminescence properties are thus interesting in selection of guest

Fig. 8. Change in fluorescence spectra for **1** ($c = 5.01 \times 10^{-5}$ M) in $CHCl_3$ upon addition of L-N-acetylvaline.

Fig. 9. Change in fluorescence spectra for **2** ($c = 3.77 \times 10^{-5}$ M) in $CHCl_3$ upon addition of D-(-)-mandelic acid.

Fig. 10. Change in fluorescence spectra for **1** ($c = 5.01 \times 10^{-5}$ M) in $CHCl_3$ upon addition of different guests.

Fig. 11. Change in fluorescence spectra for **2** ($c = 3.77 \times 10^{-5} M$) in CHCl_3 upon addition of different guests.

species. The increase in fluorescence intensities of both **1** and **2** in presence of guest acids is attributed to the hydrogen bonding effect which possibly perturbs the $n\pi^*$ state of the pyridine in a destabilizing manner such that the lowest singlet excited state becomes the $\pi\pi^*$ type^{10a,b}. The relative change in fluorescence intensities of both **1** and **2** were not used to ascertain the binding constant values as in major cases the change in intensity was minor.

In a similar manner, the ground state interactions of **1** and **2** with the same acids were carried out in CHCl_3 by UV-Vis titrations. Upon addition of the acids, the absorbances of receptors **1** and **2** at 290 nm were decreased to small extent. For example, Figs. 12 and 13 demonstrate the change in UV-vis spectra of **1** and **2** upon increasing addition of *L-N*-acetylvaline and *D-(-)*-mandelic acids, respectively.

Fig. 12. Change in UV-Vis spectra for **1** ($c = 5.01 \times 10^{-5} M$) in CH_3CN upon addition of *L-N*-acetylvaline.

Fig. 13. Change in UV-Vis spectra for **2** ($c = 3.77 \times 10^{-5} M$) in CH_3CN upon addition of *D-(-)*-mandelic acid.

Conclusion

In conclusion we have shown that pyridine-based simple and easy-to-make hetero bis amide receptors can be obtained in one step in moderate yields. They are found to be effective in hosting α -hydroxy and α -amino acid derivatives into the open clefts. While the receptor **1** is selective for *L-N*-acetylvaline, receptor **2** exhibits much preference for *D-(-)*-mandelic acid. Due to flexible nature of the hetero bis amide receptors **1** and **2** the determined binding constant values are less in magnitude. We believe that the macrocyclic analogues of **1** and **2** will be more efficient in the selective recognition of the guests, mentioned in the study. Even, the placement of the fluorophore in the vicinity of the binding centers of **1** and **2** will communicate the recognition event successfully through the photo physical changes of the probe. These strategies have been considered and the work along this direction is underway in the laboratory.

Experimental

General :

All the solvents were dried by usual procedures prior to use. All the reactions were carried out under nitrogen. FT-IR and UV spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer model L120-00A and Lambda-25 respectively. Fluorescence was recorded by Perkin-Elmer LS-50B instrument. For ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra Bruker 300, 400 and 500 MHz were used. Melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

1-(2-(2-Chloroethoxy)ethoxy)butane (4) : To a solution of diethylene glycol mono butyl ether **3** (3 mL, 17.4

mmol) in CHCl_3 (25 mL) taken in a 100 mL round bottom flask, SOCl_2 (1.55 mL, 21.0 mmol) and pyridine (1.8 mL, 20.9 mmol) were added. The mixture was refluxed 10 h. On completion of reaction as monitored by TLC, CHCl_3 was evaporated and 50 mL saturated NaHCO_3 solution was added to it. The aqueous layer was extracted with 3×50 mL CHCl_3 and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 to give **4** as brownish gummy thick liquid (2.52 g, yield : 80%). Compound **4** was used for the next steps without further characterization.

2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanamine (5) : To a solution of **4** (2 g, 11.08 mmol) in 25 mL acetone-water (50%) mixture, NaN_3 (0.792 g, 12.18 mmol) and catalytic amount of tetrabutylammonium bromide were added. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h. Acetone was evaporated and 50 mL water was added to it. The aqueous layer was extracted with 3×50 mL CHCl_3 and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 to give the brownish gummy thick liquid (1.45 g, yield : 70%). Azide compound was used for the next steps without further characterization. To a solution of azide (1.6 g, 8.55 mmol) in 25 mL dry THF taken in a 100 mL round bottom flask, PPh_3 (3.36 g, 12.81 mmol) was added and solution was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere 3 h. Water (0.46 mL, 25.5 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture and stirring was continued for further 26 h. After the completion of reaction (checked by TLC) THF was evaporated and concentrated HCl was added to make the solution acidic followed by addition of 50 mL water and 50 mL diethyl ether. The solution was shaken well, ether layer was separated and water layer was neutralized by aqueous NaOH solution and extracted with 3×50 mL CHCl_3 and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 to give the crude amine. The crude product obtained was purified by column chromatography using 2% CH_3OH in CHCl_3 as eluent to give **5** as brownish gummy thick liquid (0.688 g, yield : 50%).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.63–3.59 (4H, m), 3.57–3.53 (2H, m), 3.47–3.41 (4H, m), 3.02 (2H, br s, $-\text{NH}_2$), 1.56–1.54 (2H, m), 1.30–1.29 (2H, m), 1.00 (3H, t, J 8 Hz); FT-IR : ν cm^{-1} (KBr) : 2959, 2869, 1458, 1299, 1119.

N^1 -(2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethyl)- N^3 -(6-methylpyridin-2-yl)isophthalamide (1) : In a two-necked flask (250 mL), isophthaloyl dichloride (0.225 g, 1.10 mmol) was taken

in dry THF (30 mL), and stirred for 30 min. The aliphatic amine **5** (0.178 g, 1.10 mmol) containing Et_3N (0.02 mL) and 2-amino-6-methylpyridine (0.119 g, 1.10 mmol) containing Et_3N (0.02 mL) were dissolved separately in dry THF (50 mL). Then they were added dropwise from two different dropping funnels. Addition was continued for 2 h with stirring under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction was prolonged to stir for 12 h. After that THF was evaporated and 50 mL saturated NaHCO_3 solution was added to it. The aqueous layer was extracted with 3×50 mL CHCl_3 and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 to give the crude product which was purified by preparative TLC using 4% CH_3OH in CHCl_3 as eluent to yield gummy product **1** (0.132 g, yield : 30%).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 9.5 (1H, br s, $-\text{NHCO}-$), 8.51 (1H, s), 8.29 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.13 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.07 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.74 (1H, t, J 8 Hz), 7.58 (1H, t, J 8 Hz), 7.17 (1H, br t), 6.99 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 3.70–3.66 (4H, m), 3.62–3.59 (2H, m), 3.57–3.54 (2H, m), 3.47–3.43 (2H, m), 1.55–1.50 (2H, m), 1.31–1.27 (2H, m), 0.82 (3H, t, J 8 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : 166.3, 164.7, 156.5, 150.6, 139.0, 134.9, 134.2, 131.0, 130.3, 129.0, 125.3, 119.4, 111.1, 71.1, 70.1, 69.8, 69.6, 39.8, 31.4, 23.6, 19.0; FT-IR : ν cm^{-1} (KBr) : 3337, 2957, 1660, 1537, 1454, 1302, 1118; Mass (EI) : 400 ($\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$), 399 (M^+), 298, 149.

N -(6-((Pyridin-2-ylmethoxy)methyl)pyridin-2-yl)pivalamide (6) : To a solution of 2-hydroxymethyl pyridine (0.8 g, 7.3 mmol) in 30 mL THF, NaH (0.193 g, 8.04 mmol) was added and stirred under nitrogen atmosphere for 3 h. After that 2- N -pivaloyl amino-6-bromomethyl pyridine (1.98 g, 7.3 mmol) was added to it and stirring was continued overnight. After the completion of reaction as monitored by TLC, THF was evaporated and 50 mL water was added to it. The aqueous layer was extracted with 3×50 mL CHCl_3 and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 to give the crude product, which was purified by column chromatography using 1 : 1 petroleum ether and ethyl acetate as eluent to give **6** as thick gummy product (1.53 g, yield : 70%).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 8.56 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 8.15 (2H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.04 (1H, br s, $-\text{NHCO}-$), 7.72–7.67 (2H, m), 7.49 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.21 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 7.19 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 4.75 (2H, s), 4.63 (2H, s),

1.31 (9H, s); FT-IR : ν cm⁻¹ (KBr) : 3432, 2968, 1685, 1581, 1457, 1152.

(6-((Pyridin-2-ylmethoxy)methyl)pyridin-2-amine (7) : The corresponding amine 7 was obtained from compound 6 (0.5 g, 1.67 mmol) by refluxing for 16 h in 20 mL 4 N ethanolic KOH solution. After completion of reaction the volume of the reaction mixture was reduced by evaporation of aqueous ethanol. The reaction mixture was cooled and extracted with 3×50 mL CHCl₃ and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removal of the solvent, the crude product was purified by column chromatography using and 75% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether as eluent (0.223 g, yield : 80%). The purified amine 7 was subsequently used in the next step without further characterization.

N¹-Dodecyl-N³-(6-((pyridin-2-ylmethoxy)methyl)pyridin-2-yl)isophthalamide (2) : In a two-necked flask (250 mL), isophthaloyl dichloride (0.200 g, 0.98 mmol) was added to dry THF (30 mL), and stirred for 30 min. Amine 7 (0.165 g, 0.98 mmol) containing Et₃N (0.02 mL) and dodecyl amine (0.183 g, 0.98 mmol) containing Et₃N (0.02 mL) were dissolved separately in dry THF (50 mL). Then they were added dropwise from two different dropping funnels. Addition was continued for two hour with stirring under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction was prolonged to stir for 12 h. After that THF was evaporated and 50 ml saturated NaHCO₃ solution was added to it. The aqueous layer was extracted with 3×50 mL CHCl₃ and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ to give the crude product which was purified by preparative TLC using 6% CH₃OH in CHCl₃ as eluent to 2 give as white sold (0.162 g, yield : 31%); m.p. 108 °C.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 9.75 (1H, s, -NHCO), 8.57 (2H, br s), 8.39 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.88–7.80 (2H, m), 7.59 (2H, t, *J* 9 Hz), 7.32–7.24 (2H, m), 6.99 (1H, br t), 4.91 (2H, s), 4.73 (2H, s), 3.47 (2H, q, *J* 9 Hz), 1.66 (2H, m), 1.35–1.25 (18H, m), 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : 166.8,

165.4, 158.3, 156.6, 151.3, 149.5, 139.5, 137.2, 135.7, 134.6, 131.6, 130.5, 129.5, 125.6, 123.0, 122.1, 118.5, 113.5, 74.1, 73.7, 40.7, 32.3, 30.2, 30.1, 30.0, 29.9, 29.7, 27.4, 23.1, 14.5 (two carbons of the dodecyl chain are unresolved); FT-IR : ν cm⁻¹ (KBr) : 3301, 2920, 2850, 1655, 1630, 1535, 1465, 1342, 1144; Mass (EI) : 531.3 (M⁺ + H).

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